

GATE Data Brief 2025

**First Outcomes from the
Data Collection on Open Science
(for the reporting year 2025)**

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Authors:

Julia Priess-Buchheit, Anika Müller-Karabil, Marie Alavi

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Executive summary

This Data Brief presents first descriptive outcomes from the [Open Science Learning GATE](#) data collection in 2025. It provides a brief overview of GATE's dialogical approach, followed by structured insights into GATE's community-based contributions to how Open Science is currently conceptualised, taught, and implemented across educational, research-related, policy-oriented, and communication materials, and related implementation contexts. Please note that this document presents supporting data analysis and is not the main GATE Report 2025.

The Open Science Learning GATE is a community-driven, dialogical infrastructure designed to collect, structure, and reflect knowledge on Open Science. It connects different components within a continuous workflow: the [GATE Service](#) gathers structured input from Open Science knowledge creators (e.g. educators, trainers, authors, practitioners), while [Solution Sessions](#) use these insights to support stakeholders in discussing and further developing Open Science implementation strategies in their own communities.

This Data Brief is based on data collected both through GATE's Service and GATE's Solution Sessions in 2025. Together, these components provide both an overview of how Open Science is represented in materials as well as a practice-oriented perspective on how Open Science is or could be implemented and discussed across stakeholder contexts.

The analysis for this Report combines three data strands:

- (1) an exploratory thematic analysis of open responses on Open Science guiding thoughts, collected via the GATE Service,
- (2) a descriptive overview of the selection of prompted guiding thoughts addressed in materials, including AI-related aspects, collected via the GATE Service, and
- (3) a summary of implementation-oriented insights from GATE's Solution Sessions.

The exploratory dataset forms the basis of (1) and comprises 58 experts and 133 statements. We employed reflective thematic analysis (following Braun & Clarke, 2002, 2021); eight themes were identified and grouped into three clusters: Open Science as practice, as values and societal orientation, and as shaped by enabling conditions and tensions. Cross-cutting patterns include trust in science, science as a public good, and systemic trade-offs.

The prompted data (2) indicate that widely established guiding thoughts, such as **FAIR data**, **transparency**, and **open research**, are frequently addressed, while more context-specific dimensions appear less often. AI-related guiding thoughts show a narrower focus, primarily on **reliability**, **transparency**, and **factual accuracy**. Insights from GATE Solution Sessions (3) complement these findings by highlighting practical conditions for local implementation. Across

sessions, **trust**, **education**, **knowledge exchange**, and (AI-supported) **implementation strategies** are identified as central elements for advancing Open Science in practice.

As an intermediate step within the broader GATE workflow, this Data Brief opens the dialogue by offering first insights into the current data basis and emerging patterns. Rather than presenting a final or comprehensive synthesis, it makes initial data and analyses transparent and accessible to invite reflection, discussion, and further contributions from the community. In this sense, the report should be understood as a starting point, highlighting the potential of the GATE as a shared, evolving infrastructure through which community-based knowledge on Open Science can be continuously linked, negotiated, and developed together.

The report lays the foundation for the GATE Report 2025, which will draw on the full data set and provide a more comprehensive and integrated analysis of Open Science practices and developments over time.

1. Purpose and Scope

This Data Brief provides a data-oriented overview of the first outcomes generated through the Open Science Learning GATE. It complements the conference presentation [What shapes Open Science? Living digest linking knowledge on Open Science](#) at the World Conference of Research Integrity 2026 and prepares the ground for the future GATE Report 2025.

The main data source is the GATE Service, a reflective questionnaire for Open Science knowledge creators reviewing their own Open Sciences materials and indicating which *guiding thoughts* of Open Science are addressed and how they are understood. Guiding thoughts are shared conceptual dimensions, such as transparency, collaboration, or FAIR data, that shape how Open Science is interpreted and implemented across contexts. Experts may also introduce additional guiding thoughts. Rather than evaluating materials, the GATE Service captures expert-based perspectives and links them to concrete resources. This creates a structured connection between conceptual understandings of Open Science and their practical implementation.

A central feature of the GATE approach is its dialogical design: contributions are aggregated and fed back into the community, enabling reflection on practices and differences in interpretation across contexts. In addition to questionnaire data, the report includes insights from GATE Solution Sessions. These workshop formats use GATE data and materials to support communities in discussing and further developing context-related Open Science implementation strategies.

2. Data Basis

This Data Brief draws on three connected data strands, capturing Open Science as conceptualised in guiding thoughts, represented in materials, and discussed in implementation contexts.

First (1), the exploratory dataset includes responses to the open question: *“When we talk about Open Science - which main guiding thoughts come to your mind?”* experts could provide up to three answers. The dataset contains 58 experts and 133 statements, ranging from single keywords to longer reflective statements.

Second (2), the report includes structured self-reporting data on which (general or AI-related) guiding thoughts are addressed in experts’ materials. Since experts indicate the target audience of their materials (e.g. researchers, students, educators, policymakers, infrastructure providers), the data can be organised into subgroups. While the exploratory analysis of open guiding thoughts (see 1) includes all experts, the subsequent analysis focuses on one of these specific subgroups, namely those experts whose materials address researchers and/or students (N = 28).

Within this subgroup, three sets are analysed:

- General guiding thoughts addressed in materials (N=28),
- AI-related guiding thoughts addressed in materials (N=11),
- additional guiding thoughts beyond the prompted lists (N=12).

Third (3), the report includes implementation-oriented insights from GATE Solution Sessions. These workshop formats build on GATE data and materials, providing a complementary perspective on how Open Science is discussed and further developed in practice.

Experts were recruited via purposive and convenience sampling, supplemented by snowball sampling, focusing on individuals and communities active in Open Science and Open Science education.

3. Analytical Approach

The open-response data were analysed using a reflective thematic analysis following the approach by Braun and Clarke (2006; 2021). The process was human-based and AI-supported and followed the established steps of thematic analysis. Coding was conducted manually using MAXQDA.

Eight main themes were developed inductively and used to code the material. These themes were subsequently grouped into three broader clusters. Cross-cutting meta-themes were identified to describe patterns across clusters.

The prompted guiding thought data were analysed descriptively using Excel. The analysis focuses on frequencies and proportions of guiding thoughts reported to be addressed in the expert's materials.

The GATE Service relies on expert-based reporting. Experts review their own materials and indicate which guiding thoughts are addressed. This can be understood as a structured form of self-reflection on the scope and content of materials, without involving external evaluation or scoring. Through the GATE Service, guiding thoughts, materials, and expert-based understandings are systematically linked, allowing conceptual principles to be connected to concrete implementations and interpretations.

This part of the analysis focuses on reported coverage of general as well as AI-related guiding thoughts. In addition to the selection of guiding thoughts, experts were asked to provide short descriptions of their understanding of selected guiding thoughts. While these qualitative responses are available across the dataset, their systematic analysis is beyond the scope of the present Data Brief and will be addressed in future iterations.

Overall, the analytical process is embedded in a broader iterative workflow in which data collection, structuring, and feedback are repeated over time. The aim is not to produce a one-time analysis, but to support the continuous accumulation and reflection of community-based knowledge.

4. First Outcomes

4.1. Open Guiding Thoughts

The open-response data to the question: **When we talk about Open Science - which main guiding thoughts come to your mind?** were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis following Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke (2006, 2021). The analysis resulted in eight main themes:

- Available and accessible knowledge
- Transparency and reproducibility
- Collaborative science
- Equity, inclusion and fairness (including ethics)
- Research culture and research values
- Public good
- Capacity building
- Boundaries of openness

Expert responses range from concise keywords to more complex reflections.

The themes were grouped into three clusters:

- (1) practices (accessibility, transparency, collaboration),
- (2) values and societal orientation (equity, research values, public good), and
- (3) enabling conditions and tensions (education, boundaries of openness).

Figure 1: Thematic analysis outcomes of open-response data

Across these clusters, cross-cutting patterns such as trust in science, science as a public good, and tensions or trade-offs emerge. Taken together, the data describe Open Science as a transforming as well as transformative system oriented towards the public good - carried by practices and values, enabled by education, connected through trust, and surrounded by tensions.

These results represent an initial, descriptive structuring of the data within the ongoing GATE process.

4.2. Prompted General Guiding Thoughts

While the thematic analysis above includes all experts, the following analysis focuses on the subgroup of materials addressing researchers and/or students (n=28).

Experts were asked to indicate which of the prompted general guiding thoughts are addressed in their materials (Appendix A provides an overview of the full list of prompted general guiding thoughts and the number of selections for the subgroup discussed here). The results reflect reported coverage and, by extension, which dimensions of Open Science are likely to be encountered by persons engaging with these materials.

The most frequently addressed guiding thoughts are **FAIR data** (n=23), **open research** (n=21), **transparency** (n=20), and **“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”** (each n=20). **Collaboration** is addressed by 16 experts, while **ethics, integrity, and responsibility** are each selected by 14 experts.

To illustrate the overall distribution, a contrast between frequently and less frequently addressed guiding thoughts can be observed. Frequently addressed (“core guiding thoughts”) include FAIR data, open research, transparency, and managed openness. In contrast, more specific guiding thoughts appear less frequently. These include intellectual property protection (n=7 / 25%), traceability and data confidentiality (n=6 / 21%), and CARE principles (n=3 / 10%).

Examples from the dataset illustrate how guiding thoughts are translated into concrete understandings within specific materials. For the guiding thought **Transparency**, one expert describes: *“Objectives, methods, data basis, evaluation steps and limitations, including uncertainties, are documented in such a way that other researchers can understand decisions and classify results.”*; for the guiding thought **Open Research**, another expert notes: *“All material is made openly available, with a license allowing others to re-use.”*

These examples reflect expert-based understandings linked to specific materials submitted to the GATE Service and illustrate how abstract guiding thoughts are operationalised in practice.

WHO JOINED THE DIALOGUE ALREADY?

DOREEN SIEGFRIED
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1008-7565>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18384735>

Gen_OS Guiding thought	Understanding
Transparency	"Objectives, methods, data basis, evaluation steps and limitations, including uncertainties, are documented in such a way that other researchers can understand decisions and classify results."
Responsibility	"Openness is implemented in such a way that rights, security, data protection and social consequences are given appropriate consideration and risks are actively managed."

Figure 2: Example of a data submission based on Open Science

4.3 AI-related Guiding Thoughts

Within the subgroup of materials addressing researchers and/or students (n=28), n=11 experts indicated that guiding thoughts concerning AI are addressed in their materials. Appendix B provides an overview of the full list of prompted AI-related guiding thoughts and the number of selections for the subgroup discussed here.

The most frequently addressed guiding thoughts are **reliability of research output** (n=10), **transparency** (n=8), and **factual accuracy** (n=6). **Intellectual property protection** is addressed by three experts. Other guiding thoughts, including bias-free data or outcomes, reproducibility, privacy, traceability, and explainability, are each addressed by only two or fewer experts.

A similar contrast between more and less frequently addressed guiding thoughts can be observed. Frequently addressed aspects focus on **reliability**, **transparency**, and **verification-related dimensions**. In contrast, several aspects are not reported to be addressed in the current subgroup. These include data protection, interpretability, and prevention of or limited data amalgamation.

Examples from the dataset illustrate how AI-related guiding thoughts are interpreted in relation to specific materials. For the guiding thought of **Reliability of research output**, one expert states that *"Model sharing should become an essential part of guaranteeing research reliability."* In another example, the guiding thought **Transparency** is extended to the use of AI tools, stating that *"If AI is used, it should be reported transparently."*

These examples indicate that AI-related guiding principles are primarily framed in terms of reliability, verification, and responsible use in the analysed materials, while other governance-related dimensions are less frequently addressed.

The small number (11 out of 28) of experts contributing to the Open Science-AI relationship clearly indicates that this topic is not yet described in accessible materials for the research community.

WHO JOINED THE DIALOGUE ALREADY?

AI-OS Guiding thought	Understanding
Integrity	"The combination of GenAI and Open Science (data) allows for mass production of secondary analysis. Open data is fuel for GenAI models, which only generate statistically probable series of outputs."
Responsibility	"The separation of ethical data collection and knowledge (original research) and secondary analysis (GenAI applied to Open Science and Data) leads to a separation of responsibility for appropriate usage."
As open as possible - as closed as necessary	"Open Science has - so far - pushed for as open as possible, but less attention in the Open Science arena has been paid to as closed as necessary. GenAI's ability to consume Open Data and mass produce output is having unintended consequences."

MATT SPICK
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9417-6511>
[10.1371/journal.pmed.1004851](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1004851)

PLOS Medicine
 PERSPECTIVE
Safeguarding Open Science from exploitative practices
 Danny Maupin^{1*}, Matt Spick^{1*}, Nophar Geifman^{1*}
 School of Health Sciences, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey, United Kingdom
 * These authors contributed equally to this work.
 * n.geifman@surrey.ac.uk
 Open research and data transparency are a bulwark against

Figure 3: Example of a data submission based on Open Science-AI relationship

4.4. Added Guiding Thoughts

Within the discussed subgroup, n=12 experts added additional guiding thoughts beyond the prompted lists. These responses are heterogeneous and were thematically clustered for this Report.

Recurring elements relate to **data management practices**, including **responsible data management and data security**. Further elements concern structural conditions such as **research assessment, incentives, or policy frameworks**.

Other responses include references to **publication practices, community engagement, Open Science infrastructures, and AI-related risks**. These additional guiding thoughts mainly specify and contextualise existing dimensions rather than introducing entirely new ones.

5. GATE Solution Sessions

The GATE Solution Sessions complement the questionnaire data by focusing on the context-sensitive and practical implementation of Open Science within the research communities and/or institutions. They bring stakeholders together to discuss Open Science practices and strategies informed by GATE data and materials. (Appendix D provides an overview solution examples. Overall descriptions can be found in the following reports).

Box 1: Reports on GATE Solution Sessions

[GATE Workshop #1 - Implementing Open Science for Communities](#)

[GATE Workshop #2 - Capacity Building in Times of AI: Finding Solutions with GATE](#)

Across sessions, several recurring aspects are identified. **Trust** and **transparency** are described as central elements for Open Science adoption. **Education** and **early integration** of Open Science guiding thoughts (incl. practices) are highlighted as important for sustainable change. **Knowledge and best practices exchange**, **guidance**, and **policy frameworks** are also emphasised.

Experts also stress the need for flexibility and contextual sensitivity in implementation especially on the policy and funding side. In the context of AI, **AI-based data management tools** and **AI support** are discussed as relevant, provided that they are embedded in responsible practices.

Across the Solution Sessions, the community identified a range of very concrete, practice-oriented solutions. A central solution is the systematic integration of Open Science into education and everyday research practice, particularly at early career stages. This includes embedding Open Science into curricula, teaching it as part of good scientific practice, and supporting it through tangible tools such as checklists, templates, and real-world case studies. For example, the use of *open-lab workbooks* is proposed as a concrete instrument.

Closely linked to this is the idea of creating structured support mechanisms for researchers, especially those at the beginning of their careers. These include providing data management templates, monitoring tools, and concrete examples of good Open Science practices, as well as fostering exchange between junior and senior researchers to normalise Open Science behaviour. At the same time, the Solution Sessions highlighted the importance of combining such bottom-up support with institutional incentives and recognition systems.

Another set of solutions focuses on clear and adaptable guidance frameworks. They propose developing flexible Open Science guidelines tailored to disciplinary contexts, alongside model data management plans that help researchers translate principles into action. Importantly, these frameworks should be coherent across funding schemes and institutions, while still allowing for disciplinary differences and academic freedom.

On the technical side, the sessions outline several infrastructure-related solutions. These include the development and use of trusted repositories, federated data systems that allow analysis without moving sensitive data, and the consistent implementation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) to ensure traceability. Rather than building entirely new systems, the community emphasises leveraging and connecting existing infrastructures, thereby improving efficiency and adoption.

In the context of data and AI, the community in the Solution Sessions propose practical mechanisms for responsible data use, such as consent pathways that enable secure data sharing, the use of institutionally validated AI tools, and AI-supported processes for metadata generation or GDPR compliance.

To strengthen research quality, several solutions target reproducibility and reliability. These include introducing internal “**code checks**” before publication, promoting reproducible workflows through concrete examples, and developing tools that support verification of data and analyses.

The GATE Solution Sessions also highlight the importance of community-building solutions, such as establishing communities of practice, organising webinars, and facilitating peer exchange across institutions and disciplines. Finally, at the governance level, they propose targeted funding and policy measures, including dedicated funding for Open Science infrastructure and training, as well as the development of consistent, practical policy frameworks.

6. Limitations

The data presented in this report is based on a convenience sample, primarily involving contributors active in Open Science and Open Science education. As a result, the findings reflect an expert-oriented perspective. While this might not be representative of the broader research landscape, it allows for informed insights into how Open Science is currently conceptualised and implemented within this community.

Some analyses rely on small subgroups, particularly in the case of AI-related guiding thoughts. Some categories therefore include only a limited number of responses or are not represented at all. The results should be interpreted as descriptive indications rather than generalisable findings. In addition, the GATE Service is based on self-reporting. The data reflect how contributors describe their materials and the guiding thoughts they address, rather than an external evaluation or independent assessment of these materials.

7. Outlook

The Open Science Learning GATE is designed as a continuous data collection and feedback mechanism embedded in a broader dialogical process. Future iterations will allow the integration of additional contributions, the refinement of existing patterns, and the observation of developments over time.

The present Data Brief represents an intermediate step within this process. It contributes to making current perspectives visible and comparable, thereby supporting continuous learning and dialogue across stakeholder groups. The insights presented here will inform the development of the GATE Report 2025, which will provide a more comprehensive synthesis and further support Open Science capacity building across the research ecosystem.

References

- Alavi, M., Müller-Karabil, A., van Drimmelen, T., & Fischer, R. (2025). GATE Workshop #1 - Implementing Open Science for Communities. Metascience Conference 2025 - Unconference, London. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15878607>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). *Thematic Analysis: A Practical Guide*. London: SAGE.
- Müller-Karabil, A., Alavi, M., Guzek, V., & van Drimmelen, T. (2025). GATE Workshop #2 - Capacity Building in Times of AI: Finding Solutions with the GATE. Open Science Conference 2025 (OSC25), Hamburg. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17590125>

Appendix:

Appendix A: General Guiding Thoughts (Subgroup N=28)

Guiding Thought	Experts selecting (N)	Subgroup size (N)	Share (%)
FAIR data	23	28	82,1
Open research	21	28	75
Transparency	20	28	71,4
As open as possible - as closed as necessary	20	28	71,4
Collaboration	16	28	57,1
Ethics	14	28	50
Integrity	14	28	50
Responsibility	14	28	50
Accountability	10	28	35,7
Reliability	10	28	35,7
Data protection	9	28	32,1
Fairness	8	28	28,6
Intellectual property protection	7	28	25
Traceability	6	28	21,4
Data confidentiality	6	28	21,4
CARE principles	3	28	10,7

Note: Based on self-reported data from experts (subgroup: materials addressing researchers and/or students, N=28).

Appendix B: AI-Open Science Guiding Thoughts (Subset N=11)

AI Guiding Thought	Experts selecting (N)	Subgroup size (N)	Share (%)
Reliability of research output	10	11	90,9
Transparency	8	11	72,7
Factual accuracy	6	11	54,5
Intellectual property protection	3	11	27,3
Bias-free	2	11	18,2
Reproducibility	2	11	18,2
Privacy	2	11	18,2
Traceability	2	11	18,2
Explainability	2	11	18,2
FAIR-R data	1	11	9,1
RCR circulation	1	11	9,1
Consistency	1	11	9,1
Data protection	0	11	0
Interpretability	0	11	0
Prevention of data amalgamation	0	11	0

Note: Based on self-reported data from experts within the subgroup of materials addressing researchers and/or students (N=28). The AI-related data represent a subset of this subgroup (n=11) who provided information on AI guiding thoughts. Values indicate how many experts reported that a given guiding thought is addressed in their materials.

Appendix C: Example intersected Materials

ORCID Author	DOI example material	Title example material
https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1008-7565	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18384735	Expedition Open Science Land: A travel guide for business research
https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9417-6511	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1004851	Safeguarding Open Science from exploitative practices
https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6272-0917	doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-22412-6	A Guide to Responsible research
https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3376-259X	doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1013208	Ten quick tips for navigating intellectual property in FAIR educational resources
https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6441-6716	doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1012702	Ten simple rules for good model-sharing practices
https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7531-4333	https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/T5WRH	A peer review guide - Empowering early career reviewers

Appendix D: Example Open Science Implementations Solutions and Strategies (Solution Sessions)

Target Group	Example Solution
Early Career Researcher	Using Open-lab Workbooks provides a better overview and documentation of ERC's progress and best practice examples.
Early Career Researcher	Integrate OS into early-career training and the teaching of good scientific practice
Senior Researcher	Organising internal “code checks” at departments and institutions before publishing.
Senior Researcher	Federated data systems: analyse the data submitted, while the data stays in the system
Senior Researcher	Develop trusted, local repositories using anonymised or simulated data and AI-supported search functions to be used for research

	purposes (query (patient) data, identify cohorts of patients exhibiting similar clinical profiles, and assess suitability for research).
Open Access Officer	Establish persistent identifiers (PID) and requirements at various sectors of the research ecosystem, including leveraging AI to capture additional information
Open Access Officer	(AI) tools for reproducibility checks, including the validity of data and the analysis
ERC, Senior Researchers, Librarians	Offer training for researchers on licensing (Creative Commons), ethical and responsible data use, and AI integration in (open) research.
ERC, Senior Researchers, Librarians	Promote institutionally validated AI tools for secure data management and metadata generation; use AI to make unpublished data GDPR-compliant while maintaining responsible use.